

DR. PREETI YADAV, Professor, Amity University Rajasthan, Jaipur-302018 (Rajasthan)
py1717@rediffmail.com

DR. JEET SINGH, Officiating Principal & Head, Department of Commerce, Mahamaya
Government Degree College, Sherkot, Distt. Bijnor – 246747 (U.P.) : jsy2626@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT

The fourth industrial revolution is based on data and the manner in which it is gathered, collected and analyzed and the way in which the right decisions are taken has become the competitive factor. The source of competitive advantage is through the embedding of products with digital services. In the decades just passed, manufacturing / production systems have been steadily supplemented by information technology support instruments. The expected role of Information Technology in organizations has transformed the working conditions and efficiency of the organizations in this Industry 4.0. Industry 4.0 is being existed as an overall transformation by digitalization and automation of every part of the organization, as well as the process of manufacturing. Multi National Companies that use concepts of uninterrupted improvement and have high principles for research and development will accept the concept of Industry 4.0 and make themselves even more competitive in the market place. This becomes possible by introducing self-optimization, self-cognition and self-customization into the industry. Industry 4.0 is a concept relating to the idea of industrial revolution, which aims at the integration of production processes with the Information Technologies and Automated Techniques. In other words, it combines manufacturing methods with ICT. Industry 4.0 which leads to innovative production process makes it easy to produce products which are unique and of excellent quality and at a reasonable price. The present paper highlights the concept and features of Industry 4.0. The paper looks into the changes that will occur by applying Industry 4.0. The paper concludes with the fact that Industry 4.0 is the future of manufacturing worldwide which combined existing ideas and procedures with a new value chain which plays a fundamental role to alter whole value chains of life cycle of products while developing new and innovative products and services in the manufacturing industry.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Internet of Services, Big Data, Industry 4.0, Augmented Reality.

INTRODUCTION

At present the fourth industrial revolution is taken place. Fourth is in the sense of its innovative and qualitative nature. The changes which are taking place involves the production process which is managed and supervised in an integrated way and is combined, yet flexible. To be competitive in the global world manufacturing companies need to persistently evolve their production systems and accommodate the changing demands of the market. These all changes have a large effect on industry as well as on markets, in addition affecting the whole life cycle of the product, result in the new innovative means of production and operating the business in the light of improvement in processes, thus increasing the competitiveness of the organization. Though computers, robots, automation were existed for many decades but now internet leads to the innovative use of these things.

The fourth industrial revolution is based on data and the manner in which it is gathered, collected and analyzed and the way in which the right decisions are taken has become the competitive factor. The source of competitive advantage is through the embedding of products with digital services. In the decades just passed, manufacturing / production systems have been steadily supplemented by information technology support instruments. The expected role of Information Technology in organizations has transformed the working conditions and efficiency of the organizations in this Industry 4.0.

PURPOSE OF INDUSTRY 4.0

The main purpose of Industry 4.0 is to attain effectiveness and improvements in terms of automation and operational activities. In other words, we can say that the concept of Industry 4.0 is an umbrella term for a new industrial model which embraces a set of future industrial developments including:

- Robotics,
- Augmented Reality.
- Big Data,
- the Internet of Things (IoT),
- the Internet of Services (IoS),
- Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS),
- Cloud Manufacturing.

The adoption of these above technologies is crucial for the development of more intelligent production processes, which includes machines, devices, modules of production and products which are able to independently swap information, prompt actions and manage each other, thus leads to an intelligent and innovative manufacturing environment in an organization.

Before the introduction of Industry 4.0, there were three former industrial revolutions that have led to changes of model in the field of manufacturing:

- mechanization through steam power and water,
- mass production in assembly lines and
- automation using IT.

Industry 4.0 is being existed as an overall transformation by digitalization and automation of every part of the organization, as well as the process of manufacturing. MNCs that use concepts of uninterrupted improvement and have high principles for research and development will accept the concept of Industry 4.0 and make themselves even more competitive in the market place. This becomes possible by introducing self-optimization, self-cognition, and self-customization into the industry.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The present study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To understand the concept of Industry 4.0;
- To highlight features of Industry 4.0;
- To look into the changes that will occur by applying Industry 4.0
- To analyze the process of Industry 4.0

FEATURES OF DIFFERENT INDUSTRY REVOLUTIONS

The features of different industrial revolutions are highlighted herein below:

Table 1

Industry 1.0	Industry 2.0	Industry 3.0	Industry 4.0
The first industrial revolution began with the mechanization and mechanical power generation in 1800s. It leads to the shift from manual work to the first manufacturing processes; mainly in textile industry. The main driver of change is an improved quality of life.	The second industrial revolution was triggered by electrification that enabled industrialization and mass production. Second industrial revolution through the introduction of a division of labour and mass production with the help of electrical	The third industrial revolution is characterized by the digitalization with introduction of automation and microelectronics. In manufacturing activity, this facilitates flexible production, where different types of products are	Now we are in the fourth industrial revolution that was triggered by the development of ICT (Information and Communications Technologies). Its technological basis is smart automation of cyber-physical systems with decentralized control

<p>First industrial revolution through the introduction of mechanical production facilities with the help of water and steam power.</p>	<p>energy.</p>	<p>manufactured on flexible production lines with programmable machines. Third industrial revolution through the use of electronic and IT systems that further automate production.</p>	<p>and advanced connectivity. Due to this new technology the industrial production systems leads to reorganization of classical hierarchical automation systems to self-organizing cyber physical production system that permits flexible mass customized production as well as flexibility in the quantity of production.</p>
---	----------------	---	--

DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTIONS

Historical data reveals that:

- Industry 1.0 i.e. the first industrial revolution was concerned with steam machine invention which leads to significant level of mechanization as compared to the previous level of industry.
- Industry 2.0 i.e. the second industrial revolution was concerned with the commencement of mass production in 19th century using the electricity and assembly line creation.
- Industry 3.0 i.e. the third industrial revolution was concerned with inventing Information Technology and introducing technology into the production along with usage of automation in processes.
- Industry 4.0 i.e. the fourth industrial revolution can be portrayed as practice of Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) connected with the digitalisation and the Internet of Things (IoT) concept.

It is to be noted that development time of the industry 1.0 was huge, as it took ages to invent steam powered machines. Between industry 1.0 and industry 2.0 versions there was a gap of nearly 100 years. Industry 3.0 was introduced after 70 years and now present industry 4.0 concept after 30 - 40 years from industry 3.0. It is possible that in the short span of time an introduction of 5.0 version can be expected.

When we look at the history of Industry 4.0, it was initially developed by the Government of Germany to create a sound framework of policy to maintain industrial competitiveness of Germany on the world global market.

INDUSTRY 4.0 CONCEPT

Industry 4.0 is a concept relating to the idea of industrial revolution, which aims at the integration of production processes with the Information Technologies and Automated Techniques. In other words, it combines manufacturing methods with ICT. Industry 4.0 which leads to innovative production process makes it easy to produce products which are unique and of excellent quality and at a reasonable price. So, we can say that smart as well as digitally connected systems and processes serves as the technological base for this concept. Industry 4.0 also redefines the entire product life cycle from innovative idea to development, production, use and maintenance and ending on recycling of the product. For better understanding this idea the development of the Industry 4.0 concept was shown in the figure below:

			It is being presented as an overall change by digitalization and automation of every part of the company, as well as the manufacturing process.
		It is a direct result of the huge development in computers and ICT industries for many countries	ICT Mass Custom Production
	The railways benefitted to a great extent. The mass production of steel helped introduce railways into the industrial system which led to mass production at large.	Micro Electronics Flexible Production	Smart Automation
Helped in mechanical production and improved the agriculture sector to a great extent.	Electricity Mass Production	Digitalization, Electronic Automation	On the basis of cyber-physical production systems, merging of real and virtual worlds.
Improved quality of life	Electrification, Industrialization	Through application of electronics and IT to further automate production.	4th Industrial Revolution
Mechanization, Mechanical Power Generation.	Through introduction of mass production with the help of electrical energy	3rd Industrial Revolution	Today
Through introduction of mechanical production facilities with the help of water and steam power.	2nd Industrial Revolution	1960s	
1st Industrial Revolution	1900s		
1800s			

Figure 1

ORIGIN OF INDUSTRY 4.0 CONCEPT

The Industry 4.0 concept comes from Germany since Germany has one of the most aggressive and competitive manufacturing industries in the world and is even a global leader in the sector of manufacturing equipments. Industry 4.0 is a strategic and deliberate initiative of the Government of Germany that conventionally supports development of the industrial sector. In this sense, Industry

4.0 can also be seen as an action towards sustaining Germany's position as one of the most influential and prominent countries in the manufacturing of machines and automobiles.

In the year 2011, the basic concept was first presented at the Hannover fair. Since its inception, Industry 4.0 is a common discussion topic in academic, research and industry communities at many different occasions in Germany. The initiative is to exploit the potentials of new technologies and concepts such as:

- Availability of Internet and use of Internet of Things
- Integration and amalgamation of processes both technical and business in the organizations/ companies,
- Virtualization as well as digital mapping of the real world,

Apart from natural significance of digitalization and new technologies, the introduction of Industry 4.0 is also connected with the fact that many exploited possibilities for reducing the losses and increasing the profits in the manufacturing concern are almost exhausted and new innovative possibilities have to be found and applied. For instance, the production costs came down with the introduction of just-in-time production, with the adoption of the concepts relating to lean production and mainly by outsourcing the production to countries with lower factory costs. When we look at the decreasing costs of industrial production, Industry 4.0 is a very useful solution. It is expected that, Industry 4.0 factory could result in decrease of:

- production costs by 10-30%,
- logistic costs by 10-30%,
- quality management costs by 10-20%.

There are also a number of other merits and reasons for the adoption of this concept including:

- (1) a shorter time-to-market for the new products,
- (2) an improved customer responsiveness,
- (3) enabling a custom mass production without drastically increasing overall manufacturing costs,
- (4) more flexible and congenial working environment, and
- (5) use of natural resources and energy more efficiently

THE CHANGES THAT WILL OCCUR BY APPLYING INDUSTRY 4.0

Industry 4.0 focuses on the life cycle of a product, instead of focusing on the production or manufacturing process. On the fundamentals of lean production, company can build smart production. In smart production, leader will take decisions as per the information available, not just on the basis of experience. The important changes that we expect in the manufacturing operations are highlighted herein below:

Table 2

Industry 3.0	Industry 4.0
Plan	Act
Lean Manufacturing	Smart Manufacturing
Save Money	Create New Streams of Generating Revenue
Manufacturing Process	Product Lifetime
Decide by Experience	Decide by Information
Simplify IT	Smart Service Platform
IT for Processes	IT for Products
Monolithic MES / MOM Packages	Assistance System
Defined Communications Relationships	Collaborative Infrastructure
Decisions are Retrospective	Decisions are Real time

CHANGING OF INDUSTRY

Table 3

Items	Traditional Manufacturing	Industry 4.0 Manufacturing
Process	Rigid and Manual	Agile and Automated

Product	Standardized	Personalized and customized
Scale of factories	Large factories at centralized locations	Small factories at decentralized locations
Success metric	Low cost and high efficiency	High return on capital employed
Supply chain	Stock based planning	Dynamic and predictive
Client relationship	Low and indirect	High and direct

CHANGES WITH ADOPTION OF INDUSTRY 4.0

Table 4

S. No.	Activity	Features
1	Automated Production	Assembly lines to be equipped with robots, humanoids and machines
2	Connected Machines	Machines connected over a network will coordinate to optimize production
3	3D Printing	Manufacture complex parts in one-go without any assembly
4	Predictive Maintenance	Continuous machine monitoring and data analysis to reduce downtime
5	Big Data	Actions based on historical data to optimize production
6	Production Simulation	Simulation and optimization of production lines through softwares
7	Smart Transport System	Automated transportation of raw material / final products
8	Networked Supply Chain	Monitoring and sharing data of complete supply chain

PROCESS OF INDUSTRY 4.0

The process of Industry 4.0 is mentioned herein below:

1. **Acquire Data and Process it:** This process involves collection as well as analysis of data on processes, products, quality, manufacturing resources along with employees. The motive here is for process as well as improvement in quality of products.
2. **Assistance Systems:** This process involves technologies that help and support human resource at workplace and support them to focus mainly on their core tasks i.e. smart phones, tablet, etc.
3. **Networking and Integration of Departments:** This process involves maintaining digital connection between various sectors, sections, departments, and different supply chains. The motive of this process is to improve the coordination, transparency and collaboration, among various sectors, sections and departments.
4. **Decentralization and Service Orientation:** In this process products and processes are separated into modules. The control system is decentralized.
5. **Self Organization and Autonomy:** In this process intelligence products control their own production. The data is automatically analyzed and the system reacts accordingly.

KEY STRATEGY OF INDUSTRY 4.0

Figure 2

CHARACTERISTICS OF INDUSTRY 4.0

Industry 4.0 is the future of global manufacturing. It is the new normal era of automation, of the digitalized factory and digitalized products. There are 9 characteristics for industry as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3

1. **Cyber-Physical System (CPS):** In this system, each production has sensors installed in the whole physical aspects so as to connect the physical things with virtual models. Cyber-Physical System also acts as a foundation to create Internet of Things which can be combined to become the Internet of Services.
2. **Internet of Things (IoT):** There is a combination of manufacturing industry and Internet of Things technology in Industry 4.0. In manufacturing process there is a combination of Internet of Things and Internet of Services and from here industry 4.0 was initiated. IoT can provide advanced connectivity of physical objects, services, systems, data sharing, etc.
3. **Internet of Services (IoS):** It is an important component in the automotive industry. IoS works as a service vendor in order to provide services through the internet as per the kind of digitalization services. These services are available on demand around business models.
4. **Big Data and Analytics:** In case of predictive manufacturing, big data analytics is very helpful as well as an important direction for industrial technology development through Internet development. This results in production of huge amounts of information daily where traditional methods for current processing and analysis is unable to cope with. Due to which big data is now a hot topic in Industry 4.0.
5. **Augmented Reality (AR):** With respect to technological companies, Augmented Reality has begun to be looked as one of the most promising business to be heavily invested in. As it leads to reduced time needed for maintenance work as well as reduction of potential errors, Augmented Reality can bring huge support for maintenance works in business. It also leads to high accuracy and low frequency of maintenance.
6. **Autonomous Robots:** Nowadays current robots are easier to operate in multiple fields because they have higher flexibility and advance functions. In Industry 4.0, robots will interact and communicate with each other as well as collaborate actively with human beings as per the guidance provided by handlers. These robots are cheaper and more sophisticated in nature to achieve better abilities as compared to those presently used in the manufacturing sector.
7. **Additive Manufacturing (3D Printing):** Additive manufacturing is among the crucial tools to embrace Industry 4.0 as Industry 4.0 is inspiring the exploitation of smart production systems and advanced data technologies. The progression of cyber technology has encouraged the transition to Industry 4.0.
8. **Cloud Computing (CM):** It is a new system logic that provides a huge space of storage for the user. To access these resources, a small amount of money is needed by the individuals and enterprises. The technology is improving day by day so its performance, however, the functionality of machine data will continue to be stored into the cloud storage system, leading production systems to be more data-driven. Cloud computing is gradually becoming a great concern for many organizations during their data systems built. Though traditionally the software was not kept in clouds, the amount of applications being developed in clouds is gradually increasing day by day.
9. **Simulation:** Simulation is a way out for running a virtual or real system or process to find out the output of the modeled process or system. Simulations are basically done by using real time data to showcase the real world in a simulation model, that include machines, products and human beings.

EMERGING EIGHT TECHNOLOGIES

Technologies having the biggest impact on the people and society right now.

Figure 4

REVOLUTIONIZING INDUSTRY THROUGH INTERNET OF THINGS

Internet of Things will revolutionize the industry in Industry 4.0 regime.

Technology

- Robotics – Definitely will replace human beings on assembly line
- 3D Printing – Helpful in manufacturing customized products and components
- Big Data – Collecting and handling performance considerations and parameters
- Analytics – Understanding and analysis of collected data and information

Process

- Regular communication – Data exchange between components, systems and people
- Decentralized decision making – Concerned with routine and daily decisions
- Standardization – Easy way of customization of products and components
- Smart Transport System - Automated movement of raw material as well as final products

People

- Increased efficiency – Reduction in labour cost per unit along with efficiency of labour
- Skill Development – Updating skills, re-skilling, improvement, continuous learning & change of attitude and mindset
- To handle disruptions – Monitoring, analysis, comparing the results with standards and taking corrective actions

CONCLUSION

To conclude we can say that Industry 4.0 is the future of manufacturing worldwide which combined existing ideas and procedures with a new value chain which plays a fundamental role to alter whole value chains of life cycle of products while developing new and innovative products and services in the manufacturing industry. This results in the connection and coordination of systems to things that create active control within the company. Industry 4.0 portrayed a future scenario of manufacturing products that is characterized by the facet of a new level of organizing, controlling altering and transforming the whole range of value chain with the life cycle of products ensuring higher productivity in the organization as well as flexibility through three varieties of effective integration which are vertical, horizontal and end-to-end engineering amalgamation.

REFERENCES

Vol. 51, No.1(VI) January – June 2021

- 1) Pedersen, M.R.; Nalpantidis, L.; Andersen, R.S.; Schou, C.; Bøgh, S.; Krüger, V.; Madsen, O. Robot skills for manufacturing: From concept to industrial deployment. *Robot. Comput.-Integr. Manuf.* 2016, 37, 282–291.
- 2) Slusarczyk, B. Industry 4.0—Are we ready? *Pol. J. Manag. Stud.* 2018, 17.
- 3) Deloitte. Industry 4.0, Challenges and Solutions for the Digital Transformation and Use of Exponential Technologies; Deloitte: Swiss, Zurich, 2015.
- 4) Geissbauer, R.; Vedso, J.; Schrauf, S. Industry 4.0: Building the Digital Enterprise. 2016 Global Industry 4.0 Survey. What We Mean by Industry 4.0/Survey Key Findings/Blueprint for Digital Success. Retrieved from PwC. 2016. Available online: <https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/industries/industries-4.0/landing-page/industry-4.0-building-your-digital-enterprise-april-2016.pdf> (accessed on 12 March 2018).
- 5) Monostori, L. Cyber-physical production systems: Roots, expectations and R&D challenges. *Procedia CIRP* 2014, 17, 9–13.
- 6) Nick, G.; Pongrácz, F. How to Measure Industry 4.0 Readiness of Cities. *Int. Sci. J. Ind. 4.0* 2016, 2, 64–68. Available online: <http://industry-4.eu/winter/sbornik/2016/2/16.HOW%20TO%20MEASURE%20INDUSTRY%204.0%20READINESS%20OF%20CITIES.pdf> (accessed on 12 March 2018).
- 7) Berger, R. Industry 4.0: The New Industrial Revolution—How Europe Will Succeed; Roland Berger Strategy Consultants: Munich, Germany, 2014; pp. 1–24. Available online: https://www.rolandberger.com/publications/publication_pdf/ro (accessed on 12 March 2018).
- 8) Pereira, A.; Romero, F. A review of the meanings and the implications of the Industry 4.0 concept. *Procedia Manuf.* 2017, 13, 1206–1214.
- 9) Weyer, S.; Schmitt, M.; Ohmer, M.; Gorecky, D. Towards Industry 4.0-Standardization as the crucial challenge for highly modular, multi-vendor production systems. *IFAC-Papers Online* 2015, 48, 579–584. [1]
- 10) G. Oricchio, S. Lugaresi, A. Crovetto, S. Fontana, “SME Funding The Role of Shadow Banking and Alternative Funding Options”, Palgrave Macmillan UK, pp. 7-41, 2016. [2] Federal Government of Germany, Information on Industrie 4.0, available on-line www.bmwi.de/Redaktion/DE/Dossier/industrie-40.html (accessed 26.02.2017).
- 11) Gorecky, D., Schmitt, M., Loskyll, M. and Zühlke, D. Human-Machine-Interaction in the Industry 4.0 Era. 12th IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics, 2014, 289–294.
- 12) Liao, Y., Deschamps, F., Freitas, E.D. and Loures, R. Past, present and future of Industry 4.0 - a systematic literature review and research agenda proposal. *International Journal of Production Research* 55 (12), (2017) 3609–3629.
- 13) Marcos, M., Suárez, S., Marcos, M., Fernández-miranda, S. S., Marcos, M., Peralta, M. E. and Aguayo, F. The challenge of integrating Industry in the degree of Mechanical Engineering. *Procedia Manufacturing* 13 (1) (2017) 1229–1236.